

CONTROL OF THE INTERPHASE INTERACTION AND MORPHOLOGY IN THE ORGANIC-INORGANIC POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The organic-inorganic polymers based on epoxy networks and (a) silica generated in situ by the sol-gel process or (b) polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane (POSS) units were synthesized and characterized. Interphase interaction and morphology of the nanostructured hybrids were controlled and the factors governing structure and properties of these nanocomposites are discussed.

Keywords: Organic-inorganic polymer, interphase interaction, nanocomposite, POSS

INTRODUCTION

Organic-inorganic (O-I) polymers are nanostructured systems prospective for synthesis of multifunctional materials. The hybrid polymers involving inorganic nanodomains dispersed in a polymer matrix are typical nanomaterials showing extraordinary properties under optimum conditions. Both nano- and microstructure of the nanocomposite are of importance in optimizing the material properties. In order to achieve desirable material characteristics, however, a sufficiently strong interface interaction is necessary. Therefore, control of the interaction between phases and morphology of hybrids are of crucial importance.

We have studied two types of the O-I polymers based on epoxy networks : (a) the hybrids prepared by in situ generation of the silica structure by the sol-gel process within the network, and (b) the networks containing well defined inorganic nanobuilding blocks - polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxanes (POSS). The epoxy-amine networks were used as an organic matrix to be reinforced with an inorganic phase. We have followed formation of the epoxy-silica/POSS nanocomposites and determined the resulting structure and interaction between phases. Control of the interphase interaction and evaluation of its effect on morphology and mechanical properties is the main goal of this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The rubbery epoxide network was prepared from diglycidylether of Bisphenol A (DGEBA) and poly (oxypropylene) diamine (Jeffamine D2000, Huntsman Inc.). Tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) (Fluka, 99.3%, GC analysis) was used as received. Catalyst

p-toluenesulfonic acid monohydrate (TSA) was purified by recrystallization. The epoxy-POSS and aminofunctional-POSS derivatives were obtained from Hybrid Plastics.

Preparation of epoxy-silica hybrids

The network synthesis has been performed by the one- or two-step procedures as well as by the sequential polymerization.

One-step polymerization. The reaction mixture of the monomers (DGEBA, D2000, TEOS) and water was homogenized with the cosolvent isopropanol (IP) and both formation of the DGEBA-D2000 network and sol-gel polymerization of TEOS proceeded simultaneously. Hydrolysis and condensation of TEOS was performed at a molar ratio TEOS:H₂O=1:3 in IP solutions. The reaction was catalyzed with TSA and the polymer base catalyst D2000. The synthesis temperature regime was as follows: $T=20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ 2h, $90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ 2 days, $130\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ 2 days.

Two-step polymerization. TEOS was prehydrolyzed under acid catalysis at room temperature and then mixed with the organic components DGEBA-D2000 to start the “simultaneous” formation of both organic and inorganic phases.

Sequential polymerization. The epoxide network was prepared first by reaction of DGEBA with D2000. The cured network was swollen in the mixture TEOS-H₂O-IP at room temperature up to equilibrium. The swollen network was then heated in a closed vessel at $90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 days to polymerize TEOS and to develop the silica phase within the epoxide network. Final curing was performed in vacuum at $130\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 days.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Epoxy-silica hybrids with in situ generated silica structures

The in situ generation of nanostructures within an organic matrix enables a control of the structure build-up. We have synthesized the epoxy-silica hybrids based on the epoxy network from DGEBA and D2000. The silica phase (filler) was created by hydrolytic polycondensation of TEOS in the epoxy-amine medium.

Formation of the epoxy-silica hybrid proceeds by two simultaneous independent reactions. The curing of the epoxy system (DGEBA-diamine) results in build-up of the epoxy network, and the sol-gel process of TEOS leads to growth of the silica structure. As a result, the interpenetrating or semi interpenetrating epoxy-silica network is formed. The initial reaction mixture of the reagents is homogeneous. During polymerization, however, the polymerization induced microphase separation takes place and various hybrid morphologies are generated in dependence on the reaction conditions and the method of synthesis.

The interfacial interaction is the crucial factor governing hybrid morphology. The epoxy-amine - silica hybrid networks display the interfacial interaction due to the reaction of SiOH in the silica structure with C-OH of the epoxy system formed during the epoxy-amine curing [1] as well as with -CH(CH₃)-O-CH₂- structures of the poly(oxypropylene) chain of D2000 diamine. In addition, the H-bond interaction exists

between SiOH and C-OH or C-N of the epoxy-amine network. The strength of the interaction between phases depends on the silica structure and on the interfacial surface given by the size and character of the silica nanodomains. The structure of the silica phase is determined by the reaction mechanism of the sol-gel process. Therefore, the reaction conditions of the hydrolytic polycondensation, such as catalysis, polymerization procedure, type of solvent or content of water, affecting the mechanism, are the factors used to control the silica structure growth.

We have prepared the epoxy-silica hybrids by (a) the simultaneous polymerization of the organic monomers and TEOS (by one- or two-step procedures) and by (b) the sequential polymerization consisting in polymerization of TEOS within the preformed epoxide network. In the one-step simultaneous polymerization the sol-gel process is base catalyzed because of a molar excess of D2000 content over TSA catalyst concentration. The two-step acid-base polymerization procedure consists of prehydrolysis of TEOS in an acid medium in the first stage followed by the build-up of a network in the presence of nucleophilic D2000 in the second stage. In the case of sequential procedure the sol-gel polymerization of TEOS within the network is catalyzed with the acid.

The hybrids exhibit variable and controlled strengths of the interphase interaction resulting in a broad range of hybrids morphologies and properties. Reaction conditions of the sol-gel process govern the silica structure evolution, catalysis being the crucial factor. The acid catalysis promoting mainly hydrolysis generates the silica structure with a high content of SiOH thus advancing chemical grafting between phases. Therefore, the networks prepared under acid catalysis show more homogeneous morphology. This is the case of the sequential polymerization and also the simultaneous polymerization with the acid prehydrolysis. On the other hand, the “base catalyzed” hybrids are more heterogeneous because of absence of a sufficient interaction between phases. This is a consequence of a low amount of SiOH, typical of the silica formed under base catalysis.

However, not only catalysis operates in control of morphology. The effect of catalytic conditions and synthesis procedure on hybrids morphology is shown in Fig. 1. The morphology of the network synthesized by the one-step base catalyzed simultaneous polymerization is the most heterogeneous. The hybrid involves the large siloxane-silica aggregates of the size $\sim 100\text{-}300$ nm composed of smaller particles/clusters of ~ 40 nm in diameter. The networks prepared by the two-step acid-base polymerization show smaller silica structures. The silica domains are of the size 50-100 nm. In this case the polymerization and gelation is very fast. As a result, the reaction induced microphase separation is quenched in the early reaction stage leading to formation of a fine structure. The relative rates of polymerization and microphase separation play a crucial role for the final morphology. The finest morphology of the O-I network is created by the sequential polymerization with the preformed epoxide network. The small inorganic domains of size ~ 10 nm are formed and no larger aggregates are observed in the SEM micrograph. The steric restrictions to the growth of the siloxane structures due to the rigid organic matrix are operative in this case. The silica build-up proceeds within the epoxide network, preventing an aggregation of small particles and formation of large inorganic domains.

Figure 1 SEM micrographs of the hybrid DGEBA-D2000-silica prepared by (a) one-step polymerization, (b) two-step polymerization, (c) sequential polymerization.

The in situ generated silica structures form hard glassy domains in the rubbery epoxy matrix. A small amount of the silica leads to a significant reinforcement, characterized by increase in shear storage modulus G' in the rubbery region (Fig.2). The reinforcement strongly depends on the polymerization procedure of the hybrid synthesis. The heterogeneous base catalyzed “one step” hybrid displays only a slight increase in modulus with respect to the unmodified network. The most efficient modulus enhancement was achieved in the epoxy-silica hybrids prepared by the sequential and by the two-step (acid-base) polymerizations. The hybrids containing 10 vol % of the generated silica display increase in the rubbery modulus by two orders of the magnitude compared to the DGEBA-D2000 network. These hybrids also exhibit a very strong interaction between the epoxy network and the glassy silica domains resulting in immobilization of the network chains. Formation of the immobilized interface layer of the epoxy network in contact with the silica phase manifests itself by the new relaxation peak at a high temperature (Fig. 2b).

Epoxy-POSS hybrids

Inorganic domains generated in situ by the sol-gel process are polydisperse in size and structure despite the controlled conditions of the hybrids synthesis. Therefore, well defined POSS of the general formula $(\text{RSiO}_{3/2})_n$ and a cage-like structure, were used to prepare better characterized O-I polymers. We have synthesized the epoxy-POSS hybrid networks using the epoxy matrix DGEBA-D2000 by incorporation of the epoxy- and aminofunctional POSS monomers (Fig.3). The networks with POSS pendant on the polymer chain were prepared applying the monofunctional POSS monomer (monoepoxy-POSS, monoamino-POSS) and the multifunctional POSS monomer (containing three or more, usually eight, functional groups) was used for synthesis of the star type hybrid with the POSS unit as a network crosslink.

Figure 2 Dynamic shear storage modulus (a) and loss factor $\tan \delta$ (b) of the network DGEBA-D2000 and the hybrids DGEBA-D2000-silica. 1 DGEBA-D2000, 2-4 DGEBA-D2000-silica hybrids prepared by (2) one-step polymerization, (3) two-step polymerization, (4) sequential polymerization.

Figure 3 POSS molecule. X = NH_2 or epoxy group, R – inert organic substituents

The POSS units show a tendency to aggregation in the organic medium. Structure and morphology of the hybrids depend first of all on compatibility of POSS compounds with an epoxy matrix. The interaction between POSS units results in aggregation and either (macro)phase or microphase separation of the O-I system occurs. On the contrary, the POSS-polymer chain interaction promotes a better system miscibility leading to the hybrid with well dispersed POSS.

Compatibilization of the hybrid system to improve dispersion of POSS units in the epoxy matrix and to enhance an interaction with the polymer chain was performed by using several approaches. : (a) use of the POSS monomers with the organic substituents R showing good miscibility, (b) incorporation of the multifunctional POSS monomers as junctions of the epoxy networks instead of being attached as a dangling unit, (c) prereaction of the aminofunctional POSS monomer with diepoxide to form the more compatible POSS product.

Formation of the nanostructured DGEBA-D2000-POSS networks and evolution of both the molecular and phase structure is controlled mainly by the type of the POSS monomer including nature of the POSS substituents and a polymerization procedure.

Topological localization of POSS in the network given by the number of reactive groups on the POSS cage is the crucial factor governing the hybrid structure. The octaepoxy-POSS monomers form crosslinks of the organic-inorganic network. These inorganic nanojunctions are well dispersed in the polymer matrix (Fig.4a). Decreasing POSS functionality (i.e. number of reactive groups) results in a diminishing covalent bonding with the epoxy-amine system and an increasing tendency to POSS aggregation. The monoepoxy POSS monomers attached as dangling blocks to the epoxy-amine polymer show more or less strong POSS aggregates acting as physical crosslinks. The tendency to aggregation can be effectively controlled by using POSS with different organic substituents determining compatibility with the epoxy-amine system. The strong POSS-POSS interaction in the case of phenyl-substituted POSS leads to crystalline aggregates within matrix (see Fig.4b) while POSS with flexible isooctyl substituents show better compatibility with polymer and form small domains of weak amorphous aggregates. The low reactivity of POSS functional groups (epoxy and amine) with respect to the competing reagents DGEBA and D2000 is an additional kinetic reason of formation of POSS-rich nanoheterogeneities [2]. Due to steric hindrance and the low reactivity the functional POSS is incorporated in the network only in the late reaction stage thus provoking inhomogeneous distribution of POSS.

Figure 4 TEM micrographs of DGEBA-D2000-POSS nanocomposites containing different POSS monomers. a) octaepoxy-POSS, b) heptaphenyl-epoxy-POSS

The hybrid nanostructuration was controlled also by the way of the polymerization procedure. The two-step synthesis consisted in preparation of the adduct DGEBA-aminoPOSS (in molar ratio 2:1) in the first step followed by crosslinking with diamine D2000. The adduct (DGEBA-POSS-DGEBA) is more compatible with the DGEBA-D2000 mixture and moreover the kinetic effect of the low POSS reactivity during crosslinking is eliminated. Figure 5 shows heterogeneity of the cured hybrid prepared in one step manifested itself by two relaxation bands of $\tan \delta$ curve. The “2-step” nanocomposite is more homogeneous (one $\tan \delta$ band) and display higher modulus.

Figure 5 Dynamic shear storage modulus (a) and loss factor $\tan \delta$ (b) of the network DGEBA-D2000 – (amino-POSS). (o) one-step synthesis, (•) two-step synthesis

CONCLUSIONS

The strength of the interphase interaction in both types of the hybrids was followed and evaluated by using dynamic mechanical analysis. We have shown the effect of interphase interaction on structure and morphology determined by SEM or TEM, and proved the relationships between immobilization of the network chains due to interaction with inorganic domains and mechanical properties.

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References

1. B.J. Bauer, D.W. Liu, C.L. Jackson, J.D. Barnes, *Polym. Adv. Technol.* **1996**, 7, 333.
2. A. Strachota, P. Whelan, J. Kříž, J. Brus, M. Urbanová, M. Šlouf, L. Matějka, *Polymer* **2007**, 48, 3041.